

POPULATION DYNAMICS , MIGRATION AND ITS IMPACT.

Moldoev Murzali Ilyazovich*¹, Mariappan Thangamaniselvi *², Shanmugam Viswanath *³

*¹ Professor , Public Health Department , Osh State Medical University , Osh , Kyrgyzstan

*² Medical Student , Osh State Medical University , Osh , Kyrgyzstan

*³Medical Student , Osh State University , Osh , Kyrgyzstan

ABSTRACT

Population dynamics it means the study of the size, structure and distribution of populations over time. The three main types of population dynamics are fertility, mortality and migration. Particularly, the population migration have significant impacts on human population health. It can lead to changes in population demographics, increased risk of disease transmission. These are two important thing for the intervention of public health policies . This review give information about the knowledge on population dynamics, migration and their impact on human population health.

Keywords : Population dynamics, Fertility, Mortality, Migration and its types, factors, impact.

INTRODUCTION

Population is a group of individual of the same species living in the same geographic area. It undergo three distinct phases of their life cycle: **Growth, stability and decline**. The study of the factors that affecting the three phases is known as **POPULATION DYNAMICS**. Nearly all the populations tend to grow exponentially as long as there are resources available. Stability is the longest phase of the population's life cycle. Decline is the decrease in the number of individuals in a population. The Logistic curve also known as an **S-curve** shows the effect of a limiting factor.

The demographers consider three factors to play in the process of population dynamics. They are Fertility, Mortality and Migration.

FERTILITY: Also known as **Birth rate**. Births are usually measured as the number of live births per 1000 people. Besides this, there are other statistical methods to calculate the fertility include **Total fertility rate**. It is a indicator of the total number of children born or likely to born to a women in her entire lifetime.

According to **NATIONAL FAMILY HEALTH SURVEY**, the total fertility rate across societies, the poor section of the society has a fertility rate of 3.2 children per woman and the wealthiest countries has a total fertility rate of 1.5 children per women.

MORTALITY: The **Death rate** is called as the mortality. It expressed in the unit of deaths per 1000 individuals per year. For example, if there mortality rate of 8.5 in a population of 1000 this would mean 8.5 deaths per year in that entire population. It can increase due to epidemics, war, etc.,

MIGRATION: It refers to the permanent movement of residence of the human beings from one are to another is called **Migration**. The humans who undergo migration are called as migrants. However, there is no accepted definition of migration but, the **UNITED NATION** defines migrants as an individual who has resided in a foreign country for more than a year irrespective of the causes, voluntary or involuntary.

There are different types of migration mainly Intenal, External and International Migration.

INTERNAL MIGRATION

This refers to the people who are moving within the boundaries of the country. In India it occurs for social, education, marriage, work and to escape from the natural disaster.

- a. **REGIONAL MIGRATION** : It involves the movement of people between different regions within the country. It includes two sub categories:
1. **Inter-regional**: Movement of people from one region to another region. For example, if a group of people move from South to North India or a group of people move from North to South India.
 2. **Intra-regional**: Movement of people within the same region. For example, many individual or families moving from rural to rural or rural to urban and so on.
- b. **SECTORAL MIGRATION**: Migration occurs between different economic sectors such as industry and agriculture etc.,

1. **Inter-Sectoral Migration**: It occurs between the different economic sectors.

Rural-Urban migration: It is one of the most prominent forms of internal migration in India. It means the movement of the people moving from rural (village) to cities and towns in search of job, education, treatment and to escape from the natural disaster.

Urban-Rural migration: It is a reverse form of Rural-Urban migration . It mostly occur due to overcrowding, high living costs. It is less occur because the old age people will return when their professional commitments completed. It is also known as **COUNTER CURRENT MIGRATION**.

2. **Intra-Sectoral Migration**: Migration occur within the same economic sector.

Rural-Rural migration: Movement of the people from one rural area to another rural area. For example, the farmers move from area to area seasonal for harvesting and planting.

Urban-Urban migration: Movement of people from the one urban area to another urban area. Mainly for the study and job opportunities.

EXTERNAL MIGRATION

IMIGRATION: It refers to the movement of people from one country to another, often with the intention of settling permanently. It increases the density of the population. It can also be called as **incoming of people to an area**. From 1995-2010 Immigration statistical review in India

- India immigration statistics for 2015 was **5,240,960.00**, a **3.59% decline** from 2010.
- India immigration statistics for 2010 was **5,436,012.00**, a **8.23% decline** from 2005.
- India immigration statistics for 2005 was **5,923,642.00**, a **7.61% decline** from 2000.
- India immigration statistics for 2000 was **6,411,272.00**, a **7.78% decline** from 1995.

EMIGRATION: It refers to the people moving from their own country to another places for their settlement. Emigration reduces the density of the population. India ranks second among the world's largest sending countries for students, after China.

Table 2: Year wise distribution of Indian Migrants in GCC Countries

Country/Year	2018	2019	2020	Total
UAE	112059	76112	15167	203338
Saudi Arabia	72399	161103	40703	274205
Kuwait	57613	45712	8105	111430
Qatar	34471	31810	6990	73271
Oman	36037	28392	5313	69742
Bahrain	9142	9997	2280	21419
Total	321721	353126	78558	753405

(Source: Emigrate)

FACTORS:

Migration is one of the global phenomenon caused not only by the Economic factor but also by different factors include:

- **Economic Factors:** This is one of the main reason the people voluntary moving from their own place to developing countries for their job opportunities. Due to the low agricultural income, agriculture unemployment and underemployment are the major factors that responsible for the migrants.
- **Marriage:** It is one of the very important social factor that responsible for the moving of girls from their own places to their laws residence. According to 2011 report about 49.35 percent people shifted their residence after marriage.

- **Education and Employment:** Due to the lack of education and employment most of the people migrate from the rural area to the urban area for their higher studies or in search of trade, transport and services. The small scale industry like cottage industry that provide work for the major rural peoples. About 1.77 percent people migrated for education in 2011.
- **Employment and Environmental disaster:** People are forcefully migrating from their own places to the different countries due to the environmental disaster include flood, drought, and so on., for their shelter.
- **Political Factors:** This may encourage or discourage the migration. In India, 'sons of the soil policy' by the State government that affect the migration from other states. Even in Calcutta, the Bengali Marwari conflict will have far reaching implications.

Other factors include pull and push factors, Socio Cultural Factors, Lack of security and Urbanization.

IMPACTS:

- **Access to Healthcare Services:** Migrants who are moving for their treatment purpose they have better healthcare system that improve the health outcomes and increased life expectancy. It's a positive effect of the healthcare services. And the migrants may face the barriers like language, financial constraints this increase the risk of untreated conditions, higher rates of disease.
- **Mental Health:** Some migrants can get better life and safer environments that help in improving the mental health . Sometimes, they may develop psychological stress due to the separation from their family, social isolation and cultural adjustment. They may face the challenges include insecurity, uncertainty about the future which are responsible for the depression, anxiety.
- **Health Inequities:** Migrants who are at lower income group are at the higher risk of health inequities. They face problems include poverty, poor working condition which increases vulnerability to various diseases.
- **Exposure to new Health risk:** Migrants they have some knowledge about own countries which are useful for the new country to where they are integrating. Sometimes the migrants at high risk of the diseases to which they are not exposed to in their own countries.

Other impacts include Chronic Diseases and Lifestyle Changes, Social Determinants of Health, Vaccination and Preventive Healthcare.

CONCLUSION:

Population dynamics and migration have profound impacts on social, economic, and environmental systems. Understanding these complex relationships is crucial for developing effective policies and interventions that promote sustainable development, improve health outcomes, and enhance the well-being of individuals and communities. By examining the

drivers and consequences of population migration, we can better address the challenges and opportunities arising from these demographic shifts.

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